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MAPPING ILLICIT CORRIDORS TO EUROPE FROM LATIN AMERICA AND THE CARIBBEAN

PRELIMINARY REPORT

JUNE 2025

EL PACCTO

2.0

EU-LAC Partnership on
justice and security

INTRODUCTION

Transnational organised crime from Latin America and the Caribbean to the European Union (EU), especially the trafficking of cocaine, poses a serious threat to security, justice, public health, and governance. Record cocaine seizures in EU member states point to Europe's increasing market for cocaine consumption,¹ a trend fuelled by an unprecedented boom in cocaine production in South America.² Synthetic drugs, money laundering, environmental crime, and the trade in illegal gold are all relevant to Europe and often see the same drug trafficking networks involved.

This preliminary report provides an overview of three major drug trafficking corridors connecting Latin America and the Caribbean to the European consumer market. It is based on an initial review of open-source materials, previous InSight Crime reporting, and select interviews with in-country experts.

In 2025, EL PACCTO 2.0, InSight Crime, and the European Multidisciplinary Platform Against Criminal Threats (EMPACT) on High Risk Criminal Networks (HRCN) – particularly the Operational Action 8.3 – have decided to analyse three trafficking corridors that are key to understanding the changing dynamics of cocaine, timber, gold, and other illicit trafficking from Latin America and the Caribbean to the EU. These are: the Central American corridor, the southern Caribbean corridor, and the Pacific corridor.

Within the three corridors, a series of specific route variations have been identified as those that warrant particular attention for the pipeline to Europe. The identified routes are intended to be a focal point for further investigation into the specific trafficking methods and the composition of the HRCNs that manage the different stages of the trafficking of cocaine to Europe, but also of other illicit goods transported by criminal organisations operating on both sides of the Atlantic.

1 European Union Drugs Agency, "[Cocaine – the current situation in Europe \(European Drug Report 2024\)](#)," 11 June 2024.

2 Marina Cavalari, Alicia Flórez, Juliana Manjarrés, and Christopher Newton, "[InSight Crime's 2024 Cocaine Seizure Round-Up](#)," InSight Crime, 7 May 2025.

THE CENTRAL AMERICAN CORRIDOR

Cocaine produced in South America is transported to Central America by land, air, and sea. There, it is stored and prepared for onward shipment, either north to Mexico and the United States, or to Europe via transatlantic shipping routes. Some of the routes and cargoes make a first stop in Caribbean ports, mainly the Dominican Republic, before continuing to Europe.

ROUTE VARIATIONS

COSTA RICA AND PANAMA

Criminal groups use maritime and air routes in the Pacific and Caribbean to transport cocaine from Colombia, Ecuador, and Peru to coastal regions in Costa Rica and Panama. Common transportation methods include go-fast or fishing boats, semi-submersible vessels, and small drug planes that either land on hidden airstrips or offload cocaine on the high seas close to shore. Some cocaine – albeit in much smaller quantities – is smuggled overland between Colombia and Panama, via the Darien Gap.³

Local drug networks in Costa Rica and Panama receive and store cocaine shipments, before coordinating onward shipment to Europe via major shipping ports such as Puerto Limón/Moín, in Costa Rica, and Colón, in Panama. This process requires domestic groups to contaminate shipping containers, which they do by concealing cocaine packages within shipments of fresh fruit, construction materials, furniture, electronics, and other goods. In some cases, the drugs are hidden in the walls or refrigeration units of shipping containers themselves. To avoid detection, traffickers usually seek to corrupt port authorities and staff to ease the contamination of containers.

Multi-ton shipments of cocaine sent from Costa Rica and Panama have been discovered at European ports, particularly in Belgium, the Netherlands, and Spain. Costa Rican and Panamanian authorities have also intercepted large cocaine shipments heading for other EU countries, including Germany, Italy, France, Portugal, Greece, and Bulgaria.

GUATEMALA AND HONDURAS

South American cocaine is primarily sent via maritime routes – both in boats and semi-submersible vessels – to remote areas on Guatemala’s Pacific coast or Honduras’ Atlantic coast. Criminal groups also use drug planes to fly cocaine from Venezuela to airstrips

in dense rainforests along the coastlines of both countries, though the frequency of drug flights has dropped in recent years.⁴ Alternatively, cocaine transits Guatemala and Honduras in freight trucks driving north along the Pan-American Highway and other major roads, carrying cocaine that arrived in Costa Rica and Panama, usually bound for the US border.

Logistical networks in both Guatemala and Honduras, known locally as “transportistas,” mainly deliver cocaine shipments to Mexico via land routes. Less commonly, cocaine shipments are driven to shipping ports such as Santo Tomás de Castilla, in Guatemala, and Puerto Cortés, in Honduras, where criminal groups can exploit weak interdiction capacity and corruption to contaminate containers bound for EU countries.

KEY RECOMMENDATION FOR FURTHER INVESTIGATION AND ANALYSIS IN THE CENTRAL AMERICAN ROUTE

It is recommended to focus on transshipment routes from Colombia to Costa Rica and Panama, as these countries account for a significantly higher quantity of cocaine sent from Central America to the EU compared to Guatemala and Honduras.

³ Henry Shuldiner and Sergio Saffon, “Colombia’s AGC Squeezes Profits From Control Of Key Migration Choke Point,” InSight Crime, 4 April 2024.

⁴ Sam Woolston and Alex Papadovassilakis, “Central America Drug Flights Fall as Traffickers Shift Methods,” InSight Crime, 29 May 2024.

THE SOUTHERN CARIBBEAN CORRIDOR

Cocaine produced in South America is transported to various Caribbean islands via the northern coasts of Colombia and Venezuela, primarily using go-fast boats. The main transshipment point for EU-bound cocaine is the Dominican Republic, although other island territories, many former colonies – such as the Lesser Antilles, Aruba, and Curaçao – are also important because of their historical ties to Europe. From these locations, criminal groups send cocaine shipments to Europe using maritime shipping lanes and commercial air routes.

ROUTE VARIATIONS

DOMINICAN REPUBLIC

Much of the cocaine trafficked from South America to the Dominican Republic is produced in the department of Norte de Santander, Colombia. Prominent Colombian criminal groups move cocaine overland to departure points in coastal zones such as La Guajira and cities like Cartagena and Santa Marta.⁵ Traffickers mainly use go-fast boats to move the drugs from Colombia to the Dominican Republic.⁶

Alternatively, cocaine produced in Norte de Santander is smuggled into neighbouring Venezuela via the porous land border. Once the cocaine reaches Venezuela, it is moved by land to northern states such as Falcón, where it is loaded onto go-fast boats and sent to the Dominican Republic. Colombian criminal organizations collaborate with corrupt Venezuelan officials to facilitate cocaine transshipment. There is also increasing evidence that Dominican networks are gaining influence over the logistical chain between Colombia, Venezuela, and the Dominican Republic. These networks often subcontract smaller groups, primarily composed of Venezuelans, to coordinate transport logistics.⁷

Once the go-fast boats arrive in the Dominican Republic, the drugs are transported by land to ports or stored in warehouses. The narcotics are then shipped to Europe, primarily aboard container ships. Common smuggling tactics include a method known as “rip-on rip-off,” which sees traffickers contaminate containers unbeknownst to the sender or the recipient.⁸

The main hotspot for cocaine shipments is the Port of Caucedo.⁹ From there, contaminated containers are shipped to various destinations

5 InSight Crime remote interview, officials from the Colombian Navy’s International Maritime Counter-Narcotics Analysis Center, 21 May 2025.

6 Ibid.

7 InSight Crime, “[Dominican Republic and Venezuela: Cocaine Across the Caribbean](#),” 24 May 2018.

8 InSight Crime, “[Criminal Crossroads: Drugs, Ports, and Corruption in the Dominican Republic](#),” 7 September 2022.

9 Ibid.

in Europe – particularly Spain, the Netherlands, and Belgium. In addition, drug mules carrying small quantities of cocaine are often detected on tourist flights from the Dominican Republic to various European nations, including Spain, France, and the United Kingdom.

LESSER ANTILLES, ARUBA, BONAIRE, AND CURAÇAO

Like with the Dominican route, criminal groups in Colombia and Venezuela move cocaine shipments to departure points on the northern coasts of both countries, including Falcón and Sucre in Venezuela. From there, it is shipped on go-fast boats and fishing vessels to the islands of Aruba, Bonaire, and Curaçao, in addition to the Lesser Antilles, particularly the French overseas territories of Martinique, Saint Martin, Guadeloupe, and Dominica.¹⁰ Once the drugs reach these islands, they are typically loaded onto different vessels – particularly sailboats – and sailed to European destinations. Drug traffickers also use human couriers to transport small quantities of cocaine on commercial flights traveling from European overseas territories to countries such as France.¹¹

GUYANA, SURINAME, FRENCH GUIANA

Cocaine shipments transiting in Guyana, Suriname, and French Guiana primarily arrive on drug planes sent from Colombia, Brazil, and Venezuela. From Guyana, cocaine is shipped to Europe and West Africa on cargo ships, fishing vessels, and commercial flights. The country has also been used as a departure point for narco submarines.¹² From Suriname, cocaine shipments are primarily sent to Europe in shipping containers that depart the

10 International Maritime Counter-Narcotics Analysis Center, “Estudio de caso de narcotráfico marítimo ENC-10. Las Antillas Menores: su evolución como plataforma logística para el tránsito y/o almacenamiento de CHC hacia EE.UU., Europa, Asia y Oceanía.” Colombian Navy, 2024.

11 France-Antilles, “[Interpellé en provenance des Antilles avec 1,5 kg de cocaïne dans le corps](#),” 18 May 2025.

12 Sam Woolston and Henry Shuldiner, “[Under the Radar: What Hundreds of Narco Sub Seizures Tell Us About Global Cocaine Routes](#),” InSight Crime, 16 May 2025.

Jules Sedney Harbour in Paramaribo. From French Guiana, criminal groups use human couriers to transport smaller quantities of cocaine on commercial flights bound for Paris, although recently this route has been disrupted by heightened controls at airports. Criminal actors in Suriname, Guyana, and French Guiana tend to be smaller groups that operate in collaboration with larger, foreign criminal organizations.¹³

KEY RECOMMENDATION FOR FURTHER INVESTIGATION AND ANALYSIS IN THE SOUTHERN CARIBBEAN CORRIDOR

It is recommended to focus on cocaine transshipment via Venezuela, the Dominican Republic and European overseas territories and then onwards to Europe. These territories account for most cocaine seizures in the Caribbean. They are also among the most common transit points for cocaine shipments heading to Europe, partly because of their strong diplomatic and commercial ties to EU Member States.

¹³ Arnaud Jouve, "[France: Antilles, Guyane, les routes de la cocaïne s'intensifient](#)," France-Antilles, 1 March 2020.

THE PACIFIC CORRIDOR

Three countries on South America's Pacific coast are crucial to the cocaine pipeline to Europe: Colombia, Ecuador, and Peru. Colombia and Peru account for the vast majority of global cocaine production.¹⁴ Access to major ports in all three countries allows criminal groups to inundate transatlantic shipping routes with cocaine. Contaminated shipping containers account for the largest quantity of cocaine trafficked to Europe, though traffickers frequently use smaller vessels for different legs of the journey.

¹⁴ United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, "World Drug Report 2024: Special Points of Interest," June 2024.

ROUTE VARIATIONS

COLOMBIA

There are two predominant methods for shipping cocaine out of the Colombian Pacific. The first involves container ships leaving from Colombia's sole Pacific port in the city of Buenaventura. Criminal groups often smuggle cocaine into shipping containers stored in warehouses throughout the city, concealed in cargo or packed into the containers' walls or compartments.¹⁵ Traffickers move contaminated containers to the port, where they are loaded onto cargo ships that often stop in Central America – usually Costa Rica and Panama, but sometimes Mexico – before heading to Europe, Asia, or Australia.

The second method of transport involves go-fast boats, semi-submersible ships, and fishing vessels departing from the Pacific departments of Valle del Cauca, Cauca, and Nariño. These vessels travel much shorter distances and usually leave from densely forested jungle areas, where there is minimal infrastructure or state presence. Maritime shipments are typically destined for Central America. There, cocaine is offloaded and transported overland to ports, where local groups contaminate cargo containers bound for Europe.

PERU

Peru, the second-largest coca and cocaine producer worldwide, is another key piece of the EU-bound cocaine puzzle. Coca is grown in inland hotspots like the remote valleys of the rivers Apurímac, Ene, and Mantaro (VRAEM) and the Huánuco Valley.¹⁶ Some cocaine produced there is transported eastward towards Brazil, but most is sent by land to ports on Peru's Pacific coast, including Paita, Callao, and, more recently, Chancay.¹⁷ Balkan

¹⁵ InSight Crime interview, manager of ship inspection company, Buenaventura, Valle del Cauca, Colombia, 24 September 2024.

¹⁶ International Maritime Counter-Narcotics Analysis Center, "[Estudio de caso de narcotráfico marítimo ECN 24 - 2022: La producción de la cocaína en el Perú y su comercialización a Europa](#)," Colombian Navy, 2022.

¹⁷ Scott Mistler-Ferguson, "[How Important Is Peru's Port of Callao for Cocaine Trade?](#)," InSight Crime, 12 January 2023.

criminal networks in particular rely on Peru to source cocaine. These networks move the drug to key ports in Ecuador, before onward shipment to Spain, the Netherlands, Belgium, and Germany.¹⁸

ECUADOR

Ecuador has become a crucial transit point for cocaine produced in Colombia and Peru, primarily because of its strategic location and extensive port infrastructure. The ports of Guayaquil and Puerto Bolívar are frequently exploited by traffickers, who routinely conceal cocaine within legitimate exports such as bananas and seafood headed to Europe. Similar to Colombia, drugs also depart the Pacific coast on go-fast boats, semi-submersible ships, and fishing vessels. Boats leave from the provinces of Esmeraldas, Manabí, Santa Elena, and sometimes loop around the Galapagos Islands to avoid detection and patrols.¹⁹

Beyond the ports, Ecuador's porous borders and limited state presence in remote areas have enabled overland trafficking routes. Cocaine is transported from production zones in Colombia and Peru through Ecuador's northern and eastern provinces, often using clandestine paths in sparsely populated regions. Local gangs have established control over these corridors, engaging in violent turf wars to maintain dominance.

KEY RECOMMENDATION FOR FURTHER INVESTIGATION AND ANALYSIS IN THE PACIFIC ROUTE

It is recommended to focus on transshipment routes via Colombia and Peru. This is partly because it is impossible to understand global cocaine trends without exploring criminal dynamics in Colombia, the world's largest producer. But there is also a need to better understand the role of Peru, where research has been limited, despite Peruvian-produced cocaine being frequently destined for the European market.

¹⁸ Global Initiative against Transnational Organized Crime, "[Montenegrins continue to play a role in cocaine trafficking from Peru to Europe](#)," August 2024.

¹⁹ James Bargent, "[Ecuador: A Cocaine Superhighway to the US and Europe](#)," InSight Crime, 30 October 2019.

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